

INFORMATION SYSTEM TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF DECISION-MAKING IN EMERGENCIES**Marchenko O.***National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", Senior Lecturer
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9768-2615>***ABSTRACT**

A study of natural environment emergency monitoring was conducted, in which it was shown that the implementation of effective management using network-centric principles in conditions of uncertainty requires the use of more advanced information systems.

Peculiarities of the use of information technologies in Ukraine in the situational centers of the mechanism for liquidation of emergency situations in the natural environment have been studied.

Keywords: natural environment emergency, conditions of uncertainty, data storage and management, information system.

Introduction

The rapid growth of information volumes in today's conditions and the limited time for decision-making by managers regarding the elimination of environmental emergencies leads to the problem of monitoring emergencies and making prompt decisions regarding their elimination. That is why for the heads of all environmental protection bodies it is critically important to have technological and methodological support that would facilitate high-quality analysis of information and prompt adoption of effective management decisions, especially in the event of environmental emergencies [1].

Problem Statement

The problem of increasing the effectiveness of management decisions still remains relevant and calls for further improvement of the mechanisms for making management decisions in emergency situations of the natural environment. The processes of comprehensive reform of various spheres of public life and the state administration system itself, as well as modern military-political realities in Ukraine, are very powerful factors in the frequent occurrence of crisis situations.

Development results

Among the main stages of making a management decision are: identification and diagnosis of the problem; preparation of the necessary information for the solution; generation of alternatives for solving the problem; determination of evaluation criteria; analysis of possible consequences of the proposed alternatives; adoption (selection) of the decision; its communication to the executors and organization of implementation; control of the results and the process of implementing the decision; evaluation of the results obtained [1-3].

The construction of the information system is proposed to be carried out on the basis of an ontological approach to the formation of a knowledge base of a subject-oriented area, which provides a systematic approach to the study of a subject-oriented area in conditions of uncertainty, which gives a holistic view of the subject-oriented area.

The developed scheme of the information system for increasing the efficiency of decision-making in the event of natural environmental emergencies consists of three levels: the level of data collection and preparation, the level of analysis and knowledge base, the level of simulation (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Diagram of a decision-making information system

Description of the information system levels

The data collection and preparation level is responsible for integration with external data sources, data acquisition, and their preparation for analysis and storage. This level additionally houses the Emergency Operational Data Database (temporary storage of raw and normalized data).

The level includes modules:

- emergency data collection (data collection from external resources and systems: MLA, mobile robots, external databases of the SC, SES, possibly weather probes or other environmental monitoring systems involved);
- data normalization (cleaning, formatting and standardization of input data to specified formats acceptable for analysis);
- data analysis;
- data storage and management.

Analysis and knowledge base level. The central level where information is stored and processed. The level includes modules:

- knowledge base update (function for the administrator/expert to add new rules/scenarios to the knowledge base);
- emergency analysis (processing operational data using knowledge base rules, identifying threats/risks);
- decision support (forming recommendations and response plans based on the knowledge base and analysis).

At this level, the following are additionally placed: knowledge base (storage of emergency scenarios, rules, ontologies), analysis results database (storage of cur-

rent emergency status, forecasts, risk assessments), requirements database (stores reference requirements and restrictions), database of typical (standard) emergencies (storage of historical data - plans and predicted models of emergency situations).

The simulation level is responsible for the execution and initial development of scenarios and the final evaluation to decide on deployment or the need for further development. This level additionally houses the database of emergency models.

The level includes the following modules:

- development of simulation scenarios (generation of emergency scenarios based on requirements coming from the requirements database);
- initialization of simulation (loading of created scenarios, corresponding to the emergency model);
- simulation of external data (simulation of dynamic input data flows over time);
- creation of a simulation model (processing of data created in the previous module and generation of forecasts);
- fixation and comparison of results (recording the output data of the simulation model, comparing the system forecast with the expected result - what should happen according to the scenario);
- validation module;
- feedback (generates a detailed report on the failure/non-compliance and sends it for revision);
- training and deployment (preparation of algorithms for deployment, creation of training and reference materials for personnel).

Additionally, several modules from different levels were detailed, which were selected as the most important in the processes of the information system.

1. Detailing of the data analysis module (Fig. 2).

The module receives data from the emergency operational data database. The data is transferred to the data verification module and the task preparation module. The requirements validation module checks the incoming data requirements and tasks for completeness, consistency and compliance with the standards in the

requirements database, i.e. the readiness of the provided information to move to the next level of analysis.

In the future, if the requirements are not valid, they are transferred to the clarification request module, where the appropriate messages, error report, etc. are generated, and the emergency operational data database is accessed to obtain information on the clarification request. This cycle can be performed several times until the current emergency situation is maximally resolved. If the requirements are valid, they are transferred to the task formation module.

Figure 2 – Data analysis module

2. Detailing of the decision support module (Fig. 3).

The module is extremely important because it converts analytical data into actions - the formation of specific recommendations.

The decision support module receives input information from the analysis results database about the current status of the emergency situation, risk assessment. The response scenario identification module compares the input risks/statuses with typical data/rules from the knowledge base and from the database of typical emergency situations the relevant information for identifying the current situation - an important stage on which

all further actions depend. According to the identification results, the information is transferred to the typical emergency plan generation module or to the task development module (for an atypical emergency situation). Technical means/resources are added to each task from those available at a certain time that should help in eliminating the emergency situation.

Prioritization module for mandatory implementation of task priorities for responding to events in an emergency situation in the plan.

The generated plans are transferred to the decision confirmation module for final approval by the decision maker.

Figure 3 – Decision support module

3. Detailing the simulation scenario development module (Fig. 4).

data and a reference (expected) result and threat measurement models.

The simulation scenario development module creates a complete scenario that includes dynamic input

Figure 4 – Simulation scenario development module

The module receives data from the requirements database and the decision support module. The critical requirements analysis module tracks the requirements database for requirements that require special monitoring, based on this data, the scenario template selection module selects the appropriate scenario template based on the type of emergency using the emergency model database. The historical data integration module overlays historical/typical parameters on the selected scenario template. The dynamic parameter generation module develops dynamic data streams. The reference result creation module Using the integrated emergency model, calculates what the result should be for further comparison. The final scenario assembly module assembles the entire scenario using the dynamic data stream, reference result, and response time requirements.

Conclusion

An information system has been developed to increase the efficiency of decision-making in emergency situations, which allows for increased decision-making efficiency.

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